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The model of knowledge in the career choice process – a theoretical and empirical further development

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Abstract

Choosing an occupation appears to be a big challenge for young adults. For a successful school-to-work transition extensive knowledge seems to be necessary. The newly designed model of knowledge in the career choice process describes different forms of knowledge as a result of enhanced efficacy beliefs and intense career choice activities (information readiness and exploration). Along this model expectation, five different forms of knowledge relevant to the career choice will be explained. In the analysis, based on a data set with 493 young adults in grades 7-12, the five models were confirmed and acceptable proportions of the explained variance were determined. For the practice of career guidance and counseling, these results mean that intervention should aim at strengthening the self-efficacy. Therefore, concrete pedagogical intervention possibilities and ideas for increasing self-efficacy are presented.

Keywords

career choice; self-efficacy; exploration; knowledge

1 Introduction

The article deals with the question how self-efficacy and outcome expectations are related to behavior in the career choice process and knowledge. These findings should simplify a successful school-to-work transition for young adults and are intended to point out new aspects of their skills development. Based on the theoretical considerations on the first development of the model of knowledge within the career choice process and its empirical analysis by Struck (2016, 2017) the transferability of the model relationships to four additional knowledge dimensions will be examined.

If relationships between self-efficacy and career choice activities as well as knowledge can be confirmed, this results in possibilities of educational intervention for practical implementation in public or private educational institutions in order to be able to support young people in their career choice process.

2 Theoretical Background

The construction of the model of knowledge in the career choice process is based on the theoretical expectations and models of the social cognitive career theory (SCCT) by Lent, Brown and Hackett (1994, 2002) and is therefore designed as a path model. The social cognitive career theory by Lent et al. (1994, 2002) argues that self-efficacy and outcome expectations influence the behavior during the career choice process. Bandura (1997) describes self-efficacy as the attitude of a person to direct his/her focus consistently and successfully on an

activity. Self-efficacy has an effect on motivation as well as on effort and the perseverance required in problem solving.

The models of the social cognitive career theory therefore contain self-efficacy as a central/major variable. Along with the two effectiveness beliefs (self-efficacy and outcome expectations) and the career choice activities (information readiness and exploration) five different forms of knowledge relevant to career choice will be explained. The model describes the acquisition of knowledge as a result of enhanced efficacy beliefs and intense career choice activities. Information readiness as a motivational requirement together with exploration as an activity to discover the self and the environment are important conditions for an individually successful school-to-work transition.

The knowledge model is based on the model concept of the SCCT but will be modified. In social-cognitive career theory interests and goals (influenced by self-efficacy and expected results) are seen as prerequisites for achieving performance or satisfaction. Following on from this, the process variables of interests and goals vary in the sense of the scientific interest in order to be able to explain knowledge. The career choice activities, information readiness and exploration, are regarded as suitable to illustrate the readiness of the active engagement with the occupation choice. Knowledge (here: knowledge about the desired occupation) arises as a result of increased conviction in one's own abilities and as a result of intensive career choice activities and is therefore suitable as an endogenous variable in the model (Struck 2016, 2017).

3 Model development, procedure and methods

Following the theoretical preliminary, reflections of the development of the knowledge model and its empirical analysis with the endogenous variable knowledge about the desired occupation by Struck (2016, 2017), this article examines the extension and transferability of the model contexts to four further (additional) knowledge dimensions. For this purpose, the endogenous variable varies in every path model: In addition to knowledge about the desired occupation, the dimensions self-knowledge, conceptual knowledge, conditional knowledge and planning competence are used in the sense of a further development. The model fit of the five models and the proportion of explained variance of the five endogenous variables along direct and indirect effects in the model will be verified. If the endogenous variable can vary over the five dimensions of knowledge in the career choice process, while the five models can be confirmed by the analysis, this result increases the meaning, importance and content expressiveness of the model in general.

If the extension and transfer of the model contexts to other forms of knowledge, which is relevant to the career choice process, is successful this will increase the significance of the model in terms of content for the practice of vocational counselors and teachers in educational institutions.

Figure 1 The model of knowledge in the career choice process (cross-section)

SE=self-efficacy, OE=outcome expectations, Info=information readiness, Explo=exploration, Knowl= different forms of knowledge (knowledge about the favored occupation, self-knowledge, conceptual knowledge, knowledge of condition or planning competence), varies in every path model.

The empirical verification of the drawn model in Figure 1 is performed via path analysis on one cross-sectional data set of 493 young adults in grades 7-12 from comprehensive schools and high schools (mean age: 15.6 years, 51.7% female).

The questionnaire recorded nine scales with 63 items and used a self-assessment process. Five scales are part of the concept to measure the career choice competence (in German: *Berufswahlkompetenz*) by Ratschinski (2008, 2012).

These scales are as follows:

- Self-efficacy, a 12-item scale by Fouad, Smith & Enochs (1997)
- Outcome expectations scale with 5 items by Fouad et al. (1997)
- Information readiness, using a 5-item scale by Seifert & Stangl (1986)
- Exploration using a 6 item scale by Kracke (1997)
- Knowledge about the favored occupation via a 9-item scale developed by Seifert & Eder (1985)

In addition, the dimensions of self-knowledge (9 items), conceptual knowledge (6 items), knowledge of condition (7 items) and planning competence (4 items) by Lipowski, Kaak, Kracke and Holstein (2015) are used in the questionnaire.

4 Results

Table 1 Analyze of mean, standard deviation (SD) and estimate of the reliability (alpha)

	Mean	SD	Alpha
self-efficacy	3.17	0.40	.80
outcome expectations	3.28	0.43	.63
information readiness	3.51	0.37	.55
exploration	3.16	0.50	.74
knowledge about the favored occupation	2.88	0.64	.90
self-knowledge	3.17	0.52	.84
conceptual knowledge	2.86	0.60	.81
knowledge of condition	3.01	0.69	.88
planning competence	2.66	0.75	.76

Range of means: 1-4

Table 1 shows the means, the standard deviation and the reliability of the nine scales: Especially the self-efficacy and the different forms of knowledge clarified a high reliability. The results of the reliability of the scales outcome expectations and information readiness were not to be expected like this, because these scales had been more reliable in further studies, for example in Struck (2016, 2017) or in Ratschinski (2014).

The relationships between the variables were analyzed using regressions and path models. Path analyses offer the advantage of indicating the strength of the standardized regression

coefficients as well as the proportion of explained variance of the dependent variables and provide additional information on the model fit.

The analysis confirmed the five models and found an acceptable proportion of explained variance of the five endogenous variables. The model with the endogenous variable planning competence shows the best adaptation to the data ($\chi^2=0.82$, $df=2$, $p=.66$, $RMSEA=0.000$, $CFI=1.00$, $r^2=.20$), the highest proportion of explained variance is achieved by the endogenous variable self-knowledge ($\chi^2=6.81$, $df=2$, $p=.03$, $RMSEA=0.070$, $CFI=0.99$, $r^2=.37$). In addition, the other three models fit also well to the data, likewise the models with the endogenous variables conceptual knowledge ($\chi^2=9.15$, $df=2$, $p=.01$, $RMSEA=0.085$, $CFI=0.99$, $r^2=.24$) and knowledge of condition ($\chi^2=6.22$, $df=2$, $p=.04$, $RMSEA=0.066$, $CFI=0.99$, $r^2=.22$). Furthermore, the adaption of the model with knowledge about the favored occupation ($\chi^2=12.44$, $df=2$, $p=.00$, $RMSEA=0.103$, $CFI=0.98$, $r^2=.20$) shows an acceptable result, especially because this model has been verified before in Struck (2016, 2017).

The results underline the expressiveness of the model: Between 20% and 37% of the variance of the endogenous variables can be explained. The development and compilation of the model of knowledge in the career choice process is theoretically comprehensible and empirically provable. With the theoretical model development and its second empirical verification and confirmation a research desideratum could be closed. The meaning for the career choice process is crucial because the model, with its individual direct and indirect relationship expectations between the different variables of the effectiveness beliefs and the career choice activities, can explain all-important forms of knowledge needed in the career choice process. The adaption and transferability of the model relationships to four additional knowledge dimensions had been successful. Also, because of its second verification, the model can be seen more in a sense of generalization, respectively more universally applicable.

5 Conclusion

The designed and confirmed model of knowledge in the career choice process describes different forms of knowledge as a result of enhanced efficacy beliefs and intense career choice activities. In this way, knowledge (over all the five forms) is the result of increased beliefs in their personal abilities and the result of intensive career choice activities. The assumed relationships in the model of knowledge in the career choice process could be transferred to four additional dimensions, which underline the expected relations of the efficacy beliefs to the career choice activities and to the different forms of knowledge.

The results also confirm the important role of self-efficacy by explaining the activities and knowledge: Young adults are more active in their career choice process when they feel confident about their abilities and as a result of their activities they achieve a higher level of different forms of knowledge. Self-efficacy determines the level of readiness and activity to cope with challenges in the career choice process as well as the five different, relevant dimensions of knowledge. For the practice of career guidance and counseling in educational institutions such as schools or independent educational institutions these results mean that intervention should aim at strengthening the self-efficacy: After determination of self-efficacy, young adults can be encouraged and supported individually. If teachers, parents or career counselors try to increase the knowledge (and the activities) to support young adults in the career choice process, they can use the sources of self-efficacy by Bandura (1997). The first source (past performance) is the most effective possibility to increase the self-efficacy. Young adults should gather their own experience and knowledge in different vocational and career decision tasks to get the experience of being successful using their own abilities. Furthermore, teachers and parents can show positive role models with similar, important characteristics (for example background, gender and age) to improve self-efficacy (second source of self-efficacy: vicari-

ous experiences). The role model demonstrates that another adolescent has been successful in this task before, like the career choice decision or the school-to-work transition. In addition, verbal persuasion (third source of self-efficacy) can help young adults and could be practiced by teachers and parents. Moreover, for both aspects peers and peer education are useful. People in the same age (peers) can be better modeled and understood, their credibility is higher and they are more authentic in problem-solving. In general: Enhanced efficacy beliefs are helpful in contributing to education and the school-to-work transition of young adults, as they allow individuals to make independent and profound career decisions.

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